

MANGANESE SALTS OF ORGANIC ACIDS

BY SARJU PRASAD AND V. RAMA REDDY

Pickering (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 100, 235) obtained manganese salts of citric, tartaric, malic and racemic acids by mixing aqueous solutions of manganous chloride and the potassium salts of the acids. Dobbin (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 41, 934) studied the preparation of $Mn(C_4H_4O_6) \cdot 2H_2O$, Classen (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1882, 16, 315), of manganese oxalate, Chiesten (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1883, ii, 28, 1), of manganic acetate, $Mn_2O_6 \cdot Ac_6 \cdot 4H_2O$ and Amadori (*Gazzetta*, 1931, 61, 230), of basic manganese tartrate, $Mn_2(C_4H_2O_6) \cdot 6H_2O$ and basic manganese sodium tartrate, $MnNa_2(C_4H_2O_6) \cdot 6H_2O$. Dubasky and Vinogradov'sa (*Pub. Facult'e Sci. Univ. Masaryk*, 1934, No. 196, 7) prepared a complex compound $[Mn_2(H_2C_6H)COO]_2 \cdot Cl_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ by adding glycollic acid to the aqueous manganous chloride solution.

As very few manganese salts with organic acids are reported in the literature, the present investigation has been undertaken with a view to studying the preparation and properties of some of them.

Procedure.—The acids used were of B.D.H. 'pure' quality. Anhydrous manganous chloride was prepared by passing HCl gas over hydrated manganous chloride at $150^\circ-60^\circ$.

A mixture of the anhydrous manganous chloride and the excess of the acid was heated in an electrically heated sand-bath at a temperature of $10-15^\circ$ higher than the melting-point of the acid till the evolution of HCl had ceased. The product was washed free of the acid, and dried. Manganese was estimated as manganese pyrophosphate and the organic matter, found by difference.

TABLE I

Organic acids.	Compound formed.	Colour.	% Manganese.		% Org. matter.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Myristic	$Mn[CH_3(CH_2)_{12}COO]_2$	Dark black	10.62	10.77	89.37	89.23
Palmitic	$Mn[CH_3(CH_2)_{14}COO]_2$	Brown	9.77	9.71	90.23	90.29
Stearic	$Mn[CH_3(CH_2)_{16}COO]_2$	Dark black	8.82	8.83	91.18	91.17
Adipic	$Mn[(CH_2)_4(COO)_2]_2$	Black	27.69	27.58	72.31	72.42
Benzoic	$Mn(C_6H_5COO)_2$	Pale white	18.39	18.48	81.61	81.52
Succinic	$Mn \left[\begin{array}{c} (CH_2COO) \\ \\ CH_2COO \end{array} \right]_2$	Brown	32.13	32.12	67.87	67.88
Malonic	$Mn^{\circ}[CH_2(COO)_2]_2$	Snuff	35.26	34.97	64.74	65.03
Camphoric	$Mn[C_9H_{14}(COO)_2]_2$	Brownish black	22.05	21.70	77.95	78.30
Cinnamic	$Mn(C_6H_5CH=CHCOO)_2$	Deep brown	15.71	15.73	84.28	84.27
Salicylic	$Mn \left(C_6H_4 < \begin{array}{c} O \\ \parallel \\ COO \end{array} \right)_2$	Light brown	28.82	28.76	71.18	71.24

From the results it is evident that manganese behaves consistently as a divalent element and displaces the hydrogen atom of the carboxylic group in the salt formation. In the case of hydroxy-acid, salicylic acid, the hydrogen atom of the hydroxyl group was also replaced. No basic salt was obtained in any case.

The salts are stable, and are decomposed by water and dilute acids. All the salts are insoluble in organic solvents.

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CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
BANARAS HINDU UNIVERSITY,
VARANASI-5.

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